

Dock-to-Dock: Multimodal Freight Transportation in Coastal Regions

Challenges, Opportunities, and Benefits

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Abstract

The Dock to Dock (D2D) project defines the primary infrastructure for future electric freight transport solutions between coastal cities, in particular the energy infrastructure (battery charging/hydrogen refuelling) required for ground vehicles, and urban air mobility and autonomous vessels. We assess typical use cases against economic, environmental, and technological constraints. Our exploitation process involves end-users and stakeholders e.g seaports, airports, autonomous shipbuilders, and electric aircraft manufacturers. We demonstrate and assist in selecting the most promising use case for commercial exploitation to help the UK create and grow its hydrogen transport economy and meet its net-zero ambitions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Decarbonising remains a challenge that lacks technology, infrastructure, and regulation. Aviation contributes 2.1% to total human-generated CO₂ emissions. This is 12% of total emissions and while road transport emissions stand at 74% (Air Transport Action Group, 2022). The Dock-2-Dock (D2D) considers the combined aspects of route development, air vehicle performance, and the associated infrastructure as well as point-to-point delivery of goods and freight between coastal cities using zero-emission Hydrogen (H₂) fuel technology for electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing (eVTOL) aircraft and electric Autonomous Zero Emission (eAZE) ships. However, the focus of the present contribution is road and ship transportation. We assess the use cases against economics, environmental, and technology constraints.

2. BACKGROUND AND CURRENT SCENARIO

2.1 Energy mix and energy deficit

Net energy importing countries seeking net-zero targets must: a) decarbonise their current electricity consumption - which makes approximately 25% of their energy mix (see Figure 1 left illustration), b) solve intermittency issues of renewable energies, and c) expend additional energy to decarbonise the remaining 75% of their energy mix - currently produced from fossil fuel usage.

The UK's energy use is diverse (EnergyDashboard, 2022). The UK currently imports 50% of its energy. In the global landscape, the situation is even more challenging with electricity only amounting to approximately 16% of the worldwide energy mix (Figure 1 right illustration).

Figure 1: the UK and world energy mix and use.

2.2 Access to green energy - the true challenge

Most Northern Hemisphere countries face several challenges in their effort to meet net-zero targets. Domestic electricity production in the UK and most of the EU (except Norway and France) has a high carbon intensity due in large part to the need to mitigate the intermittency of renewable energy production methods. Moreover, Europe is also already a net energy importer, and it is uncertain whether this energy deficit can be reduced soon.

If Northern Hemisphere regions continue to import energy in the foreseeable future, what form is this likely to take? In addition to costly undersea cable infrastructure projects, Hydrogen (H₂) is increasingly perceived as a necessary energy source to meet net-zero ambitions.

The regional production cost of H₂ closely matches solar irradiance as suggested on the map shown in Figure 2. The same solar panel installed in Africa has of the order of 3 times the production capacity than if it were installed in Germany. Together with differences in land prices and local labour force costs, producing renewable electricity and green H₂ in developed or Northern Hemisphere countries can be uncompetitive.

Figure 2: Indicative H₂ production cost in USD by region.

H₂ can be produced cleanly from renewable or nuclear energy and used with minimal emissions in fuel cells, dual-fuel engines, or as a substitute for natural gas in heat and power applications. H₂ can also potentially remedy the intermittency of wind and solar electricity production, but it is difficult to transport and store, requiring costly very high pressures (up to 700 bar) or extremely low cryogenic temperatures (-253°C). Alternative, carbon-free, H₂ carriers such as Ammonia (NH₃) are increasingly considered for the effective and economical transport, storage, and distribution of H₂ to end-users (Fecke, Garner and Cox, 2016), especially when combined with on-site cracking of NH₃ into H₂ (NH₃ is liquid at moderate pressures of approximately 10 bar or modest temperature of -33°C). NH₃ handling and storage in large volumes are considered safer than pressurised storage (Anderson, 2022).

3. DOCK-TO-DOCK (D2D) PROJECT

3.1 Motivation and vision

The Dock-to-Dock (D2D) project funded by Innovate UK was motivated by the need to reduce the carbon footprint of transport by the major contributors such as the aviation and marine sectors. Two initiatives are pertinent to the D2D:

- The International Maritime Organisation (IMO) aims to reduce by 70% the emissions intensity of Ports and Vessels and to reduce by 50% the overall emission of the marine sector by 2050.
- The International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) has set up a Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) and intends to keep net CO₂ emissions at 2020 levels.

Battery-powered vehicles are one solution on our path to decarbonisation and it is accepted that batteries have a role to play even in heavy-duty applications. There is, however, a growing concern over the sustainability of the large number of high-capacity batteries needed to transition vehicles away from fossil fuels, as well as concerns over access to low-carbon electricity in densely populated countries, particularly, in Northern regions.

H₂ is recognised as an alternative to electric batteries and has a key role to play on the path to net-zero, either used to produce electricity in fuel cells or as a carbon-free fuel for internal combustion engines. H₂ refuelling infrastructure is however lacking and it has hampered the development of H₂ vehicles due to a lack of supply.

The project aims to create a supply-driven demand for H₂ and provide a sustainable alternative to battery-powered vehicles as the world seeks to decarbonise. H₂ infrastructure located at ports can position coastal cities at the epicenter of a future H₂-based transport economy:

- 90% of cargo trade passes through 1,200 seaports in 23 maritime EU member states
- 40% of the world's population lives within 60 miles of the coast
- The population density in coastal areas is 2 times the world's average population density
- 14 of the world's 17 largest cities are on coasts

3.2 Scope and methodology

D2D is focused on the combined aspects of route development, vehicle performance, and the associated infrastructure at ports (airports and seaports).

We use a route between Avonmouth Docks and Cardiff Docks to assess air, ground, and sea routes for the transport of cargo between coastal cities (Figure 3), using low or zero-emission electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing aircraft (eVTOL), electric Goods Vehicles (eGV) and electric Short Sea Shipping (eSSS).

The D2D use case evaluation aims to investigate alternative modes of transport:

- eVTOL aircraft are assessed against Light Goods Vehicles (LGVs) for the transport of up to 400 kg of time-sensitive cargo.
- eAZE short-sea vessels are assessed against Heavy Goods Vehicles (HGVs) for the transport of up to 14,000 kg of non-time-sensitive cargo.

Figure 3: Dock-to-dock (D2D) test route

4. USE CASE EVALUATION

4.1 Road transport baseline

Goods currently moved between Bristol and Cardiff (and more specifically Avonmouth Docks and Cardiff Docks) are transported by road using HGVs and LGVs. LGVs, or vans, typically transport lighter and smaller goods that are usually time-sensitive, such as deliveries of medical supplies, online shopping, spare parts, etc. HGVs, or lorries, typically transport less urgent but heavier and bulkier goods. The loading and unloading of HGVs are usually more involved than LGVs due to the nature of goods transported (weight and size) and the semi-rigid nature of lorry trailers. The ground route between Avonmouth and Cardiff docks covers a distance of ~60 km or ~37 miles. There is significant daily traffic between docks: 1,593 LGVs and 1,251 HGVs in each direction, every day.

The daily emissions associated with this level of commercial traffic on the D2D route are significant and consist of the following pollutant emission factors:

- NO_x, PM₁₀ (particulate matter particles are less than 10 µm in diameter), PM_{2.5} (content is less than 2.5 µm in diameter) obtained from Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA)
- CO_{2e} obtained from government conversion factors for company reporting of greenhouse gas emissions

CO_{2e} emissions from LGVs and HGVs have improved in the last years due to the European emission standards, whereas NO_x is still significant. LGVs and HGVs traffic on the D2D route emits more than 250 tonnes of CO_{2e} per day as seen in Table 1.

Table 1: Daily emissions of ground freight traffic along the D2D route

Vehicle	No. of vehicles	Emission per vehicle		Emission per day
		kg of NO _x	kg of CO _{2e}	tonnes of CO _{2e}
LGVs	1,593	239.27	40.19	64.0
HGVs	1,251	171.6	153.11	191.5
Total	2,844			255.6

4.2 Electric transport definition

4.2.1 eLGV Requirements

Electric vans (eLGVs) can be a viable alternative to diesel vans for the transport of small cargo between docks with a relatively short turnaround. Table 2 considers only battery-powered vans as they are deemed suitable for D2D and are now readily available from a wide range of manufacturers. A payload of 400-500 kg is considered for this assessment. When assuming a 25-min turnaround time (TAT), the transit duration of goods between docks using a van is of the order of 90 min as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Electric LGV energy use and emissions (payload=400 kg)

eLGV	Fuel Cell	Battery
Duration	-	60-70 min
Energy on-road	-	12.0 kWh
Energy at infrastructure (*)	-	13.3 kWh
Emissions per payload (2020)	-	3.4 kg CO _{2e}
Emissions per payload (2030)	-	1.6 kg CO _{2e}
Emissions per kg (2020)	-	8.5 g CO _{2e} per kg
Emissions per kg (2030)	-	4.0 g CO _{2e} per kg

(*) assumes a 25-min TAT for the van, with 20 min available for recharging. The minimum infrastructure required to service one van must deliver 40 kWh of electricity (fast-charging efficiency = 90%).

4.2.2 eVTOL Requirements

Electric Vertical Take-Off and Landing aircraft (eVTOL) can be an effective solution for the transport of high-value goods between docks (fast transit time and a short TAT). Table 3 considers only electric VTOL, either battery or fuel cell-powered. The table details the best-case energy consumption and emissions of a generic winged eVTOL aircraft designed to meet the D2D mission between Avonmouth and Cardiff docks. A payload of 400-500 kg is considered for this assessment. When assuming a 15-min TAT, the transit duration of goods between docks using eVTOL is of the order of 30 min.

It should be noted that if wingless eVTOL is used (e.g multi-rotor aircraft such as Volocopter), the flight duration is increased (slower speed) and the energy in flight is increased (poor forward flight efficiency due to very low lift to drag ratio coefficient).

Table 3: eVTOL energy use and emissions (payload = 400 kg)

eVTOL	Fuel Cell	Battery
Duration	12 min	12 min
Energy in-flight	52.2 kWh	47.5 kWh
Energy at infrastructure (*)	3.0 kg H ₂	59.4 kWh
Emissions per payload (2020)	14.3 kg CO ₂ e	15.0 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per payload (2030)	9.2 kg CO ₂ e	7.1 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per kg (2020)	35.6 g CO ₂ e per kg	37.5 g CO ₂ e per kg
Emissions per kg (2030)	23 g CO ₂ e per kg	17.8 g CO ₂ e per kg

(*) assumes a 15-min TAT for the aircraft, with 10 min available for refuelling or recharging, the minimum infrastructure required to service one aircraft must be able to deliver:

- 18 kg/hr of compressed H₂ at 350 bar for the fuel cell version
- 360 kWh of electricity (fast-charging efficiency = 80%)

4.2.3 eHGV Requirements

Electric lorries (eHGVs) are readily available as an alternative to diesel lorries for the transport of cargo between docks, in particular fuel cell HGVs such as 32T Hyundai Xcient, with a range of 400 km from 32 kg of compressed H₂ at 350 bar. Battery-powered lorries can also be a solution for shorter journeys such as urban deliveries or the proposed D2D route and some manufacturers are now proposing battery-HGVs.

A typical payload of 12,000-14,000 kg is considered for this assessment (average load of a TEU container, twenty-foot equivalent unit). When assuming a 60-min TAT, the transit duration of goods between docks using a lorry is of the order of 2 hrs. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: eHGV energy use and emissions (payload=14,000 kg)

eHGV	Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle (FCEV)	Battery Electric Vehicle (BEV)
Duration	62.7 min	60.4 min
Energy on-road (per TEU)	181.4 kWh	61.7 kWh
Energy at infrastructure (*)	5.5 kg H ₂	72.6 kWh
Emissions per payload (2020)	26.3 kg CO ₂ e	18.4 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per payload (2030)	16.8 kg CO ₂ e	8.7 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per kg (2020)	1.88 g CO ₂ e per kg	1.31 g CO ₂ e per kg
Emissions per kg (2030)	1.20 g CO ₂ e per kg	0.62 g CO ₂ e per kg

(*) assumes a 60-min turnaround time for the lorry, with 50 min available for recharging/refuelling, the minimum infrastructure required to service one lorry must be able to deliver:

- 7 kg/hr of compressed H₂ at 350 bar for the fuel cell version
- 90 kWh of electricity (fast-charging efficiency = 90%)

4.2.4 eSSS Requirements

Electric Short Sea Shipping (eSSS) is increasingly seen as a tool to reduce the emissions of road transport across Europe in particular. eSSS is an ideal solution for the transport of large cargo where slow transit time and TATs are acceptable. Electric vessels have a role to play with Yara Birkland being the most recent example of a battery-powered 3000 DWT bulk carrier, although its range and speed are limited and the size of its battery considerable. A 3000 DWT, 120 TEU vessel is considered, with an average unit payload of 12,000-14,000 kg. The data provided in Table 5 is per TEU, to arrive at the vessel requirement, energy and emissions must be multiplied by the number of TEU carried per vessel. When assuming a 6-hrs TAT (3 min per TEU assuming Lift on/Lift on LoLo loading), the transit duration of goods between docks using a lorry is of the order of 7.5 hrs.

Table 5: eHGV energy use and emissions (payload=14,000 kg)

eAZE	FCEV	BEV
Duration	90 min	90 min
Energy at sea (per TEU)	37.8 kWh	18.8 kWh
Energy at infrastructure (*)	1.1 kg H ₂	20.8 kWh
Emissions per payload (2020)	5.4 kg CO ₂ e	5.3 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per unit payload (2030)	3.5 kg CO ₂ e	2.5 kg CO ₂ e
Emissions per kg (2020)	0.39 g CO ₂ e per kg	0.38 g CO ₂ e per kg
Emissions per kg (2030)	0.25 g CO ₂ e per kg	0.18 g CO ₂ e per kg

(*) assumes a 360-min turnaround time for the vessel, with 300 min available for recharging or refuelling, the minimum infrastructure required to service a 120 TEU vessel must be able to deliver:

- 3 kg/hr of compressed H₂ for the fuel cell version
- 760 kWh of electricity (slow-charging efficiency = 90%)

4.2.5 Electric Solutions Performance Summary

Table 7 summarises the performance of each solution by type. For light goods (LGVs versus eVTOL) the unit cost quoted is per 400 kg payload. For heavy goods (HGVs versus eAZE) the unit cost quoted is per 14,000 kg payload. Transit time (quoted in minutes) refers to the time during which the payload is moving between docks (by air, road, or sea). The TAT (quoted in minutes) during which the payload is handled (loaded/unloaded or swapped if using pods or containers). Part of this time is available to recharge batteries or refuel H₂ tanks. The duration (quoted in hours) is the sum of transit and TAT.

When assessing the cost of various forms of transport between docks, a sensitivity analysis was conducted to derive maximum and minimum unit costs, based on the following criteria:

- LGV: low traffic (60-min transit) vs. high traffic (75-min transit)
- HGV: low traffic (65-min transit) vs. high traffic (80-min transit)
- eVTOL: high flight speed (12-min transit) vs. low flight speed (18-min transit)
- eAZE: fast unloading (4-hrs TAT) vs. slow unloading (6-hrs TAT)

The above scenarios lead to a minimum and a maximum overall duration for the transport of goods between docks, arising in a minimum and maximum cost of transport as discussed in Section 6.4.

Table 7: D2D performance summary by vehicle type

Solution	Battery eVTOL	Fuel Cell eVTOL	Battery Van	Battery Lorry	Fuel Cell Lorry	Battery Vessel	Fuel Cell Vessel
Distance (km)	32	32	63	63	63	37	37
Min. transit (min)	12	12	60	65	65	90	90
Max. transit (min)	18	18	75	80	80	90	90
Min. TAT (min)	15	15	25	50	50	240	240
Max. TAT (min)	15	15	25	50	50	360	360
Min. duration (hrs)	0.45	0.45	1.4	1.9	1.9	5.5	5.5
Max. duration (hrs)	0.55	0.55	1.7	2.2	2.2	7.5	7.5

4.3 Environmental Impact

Table 8 summarises the emissions of each solution estimated in 2020 and 2030. For light goods (LGVs versus VTOL) the emissions quoted are per 400 kg payload. For heavy goods (HGVs versus SSS) the emissions quoted are per 14,000 kg (14 Mt) payload.

Table 8: D2D emissions comparison summary (per kg of cargo)

Solution	Battery eVTOL	Fuel Cell eVTOL	Battery Van	Battery Lorry	Fuel Cell Lorry	Battery Vessel	Fuel Cell Vessel
Average duration (hrs)	0.50	0.50	1.54	2.04	2.04	6.50	6.50
Average emissions per kg transported (2020)	37.5g CO ₂ e	35.6g CO ₂ e	8.5g CO ₂ e	1.31g CO ₂ e	1.88g CO ₂ e	0.38g CO ₂ e	0.39g CO ₂ e
Average emissions per kg transported (2030)	23.0g CO ₂ e	17.8g CO ₂ e	4.0g CO ₂ e	0.62g CO ₂ e	1.20g CO ₂ e	0.18g CO ₂ e	0.25g CO ₂ e

Figure 5 illustrates the environmental impact of light goods and heavy goods transport on the D2D route, expressed as the energy used during the journey (excluding charging losses when using batteries) as well as the CO₂e emissions of each solution.

Figure 5: Light Goods (400 kg cargo, LEFT) and Heavy Goods (14 Mt cargo, RIGHT) energy and emissions

4.4 Cost Assessment

Table 9 presents the results of a cost sensitivity analysis based on various transport duration scenarios between docks, as detailed in Table 7. The minimum cost is associated with the minimum transport duration (shortest transit time and quickest turnaround), whereas the maximum cost is associated with the maximum transport duration (slowest transit time and longest turnaround). The costs are quoted in GBP per unit payload:

Table 9: D2D cost sensitivity analysis (2020 only)

Solution	Battery eVTOL	Fuel Cell eVTOL	Battery Van	Battery Lorry	Fuel Cell Lorry	Battery Vessel	Fuel Cell Vessel
Distance (km)	32	32	63	63	63	37	37
Nominal payload	400 kg cargo			14,000 kg container			
Min. unit cost (2020)	£41.6	£32.2	£27.2	£80.4	£86.7	£9.8	£13.0
Max. unit cost (2020)	£58.3	£45.1	£29.3	£86.2	£92.9	£13.1	£17.4

Table 10 summarises and compares each solution, based on average duration in hours, the average cost (in GBP, 2020 only), and cost per kg transported (in pence, 2020 only).

Table 10: D2D cost comparison summary (2020 only)

Solution	Battery eVTOL	Fuel Cell eVTOL	Battery Van	Battery Lorry	Fuel Cell Lorry	Battery Vessel	Fuel Cell Vessel
Nominal payload (kg)	400 kg			14,000 kg			
Average duration (hrs)	0.50	0.50	1.54	2.04	2.04	6.50	6.50
Average cost per payload	£49.9	£38.7	£28.2	£83.3	£89.8	£11.5	£15.2
Average cost per kg transported	12.48p	9.67p	7.06p	0.59p	0.64p	0.08p	0.11p

Figure 7 depicts the duration and cost of goods transport of Light Goods (400 kg of cargo) and Heavy Goods (14,000 kg) between Avonmouth and Cardiff docks. As expected, an eVTOL is 3 times faster than an LGV between docks and this performance comes at an increased cost of between +37% for a fuel cell eVTOL to +77% for a battery eVTOL. HGVs are 2-3 times faster than an SSS between docks (due to handling time at docks – loading/unloading), however, due to the nature of goods, this may not be critical. The transport cost using SSS is dramatically lower than using HGVs at around 1/8th of lorry transport.

Figure 7: Light goods transport cost (left) and heavy goods transport cost (right).

Table 11 gives the amount of cargo transported throughout a 12-hrs window using a single van and a single eVTOL. A single eVTOL can move approximately 3 times the amount of cargo as a van, due to the shorter transport time.

Table 11: Light goods transport capacity (12hrs utilisation)

	LGV	eVTOL
Duration of transport (hrs)	1.54	0.50
Number of crossings	7.8	24
Load transported (kg)	3114	9600

As a result, a single eVTOL can take up to 3 vans off the roads. This only marginally reduces congestion but significantly increases emissions. eVTOL is therefore only recommended to move goods that are time-critical, for example, medical supplies.

Table 12 summarises the amount of cargo transported throughout a 24-hr window using a single lorry with multiple drivers and a single SSS with multiple crew members if manned. A single SSS can move approximately 38 times the amount of cargo than a lorry, despite the longer transport time.

Table 12: Heavy goods transport capacity (24 hrs utilisation)

	HGV	SSS
Duration of transport (hrs)	2.04	6.50
Nominal payloads (Mt)	14	1680
Number of crossings	11.8	3.7
Load transported (tonnes)	165	6203

The ability to reduce the loading/unloading duration of the SSS vessel, for example, by using an automated Roll on/Roll off (RoRo) loading, could allow a single SSS to take 100 lorries off the roads. This would meaningfully reduce congestion and dramatically reduce emissions. The use of SSS in coastal regions should be encouraged for goods that are not time-sensitive.

5. DISCUSSION

eVTOL cargo freight is economically viable as an alternative to LGVs in coastal regions (hub-to-hub but not door-to-door). eVTOL offers a significant reduction in transit time (premium service) at a relatively modest cost increase. However, eVTOL does not reduce traffic noticeably without a huge expansion of the vertiport network/infrastructure. Whilst marginally reducing emissions compared to conventional diesel-powered vans, eVTOL significantly increases emissions compared to eLGVs.

SSS cargo freight is a highly effective substitute for HGVs in coastal regions or inland when moving goods using waterways. SSS should be heavily promoted/encouraged in the UK and the EU as it could lead to significant reductions in cost and emissions and a noticeable reduction in road traffic. The transit time increase is not considered an issue for this type of payload/cargo.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Coastal regions present unique characteristics that enable the use of alternative forms of transport to substitute the transport of freight by road, reduce emissions and reduce congestion.

eVTOL and in general Urban Air Mobility (UAM) have a role to play but the physics of flight inevitably results in significant energy utilisation which is not necessarily in line with the challenges faced by modern nations: access to sufficient green energy. eVTOL should therefore be limited to time-sensitive freight transportation, such as medical emergencies. For more routine light goods transport, the electrification of vans should be encouraged as commercially viable solutions are already available from a variety of manufacturers.

In our efforts to further reduce energy use and emissions (both global and local), the use of Short Sea Shipping, next coast and on riverways should instead be actively encouraged as it permits very significant reductions in emissions, cost and congestion.

Other aspects of the D2D project, focussing on energy requirements and infrastructure definition (for recharging battery vehicles and refuelling hydrogen vehicles) will be presented in future publications.

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REFERENCES

Anderson, K. (2017). Ammonia safety, a global perspective. Technion Ammonia Conference, Haifa, Israel, November 2017.

Air Transport Action Group (ATAG) (2022). Available at <https://www.atag.org/facts-figures.html> (Accessed: 14 May 2022).

Energy Dashboard (2022). Available at <https://www.energydashboard.co.uk/map> (Accessed: 14 May 2022).

Fecke, M., Garner, S. and Cox, B., (2016). Review of global regulations for anhydrous ammonia production, use, and storage. In *Inst. Chem. Eng (IChemE). Symp. Series (Hazards 26)*, 1-11.